

Evaluating the Enhancing of Quality of Life of Tehran Citizens with Radio Public Service Announcements

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Abstract:

Communications is one of the basic concepts in the social sciences, especially communication sciences, in the present era. The significance of this term comes from the fact that basically man cannot live without communications and it is impossible to build a community without communications. In other words, communications are the cornerstone of the structure of the society, which can be manifested at different levels (Bashir, 2008). Having a radio receiver, each citizen can instantly access information or cultural products since radio has been considered as a tool for social and cultural development anywhere in the world (Saghebfar, 2011).

The concept of quality of life was initially limited to the areas of health and mental illnesses, but over the past two decades, this concept has promoted to a multi-dimensional concept from merely health, environmental and psychological domains fields (Anbari, 2010) and turned into the focus of attention of a large number of study areas. Hence, more than 55,000 studies have been conducted on the quality of life from 1982 to 2005 based on the data from the Institute of Scientific Information (Rezvani and Mansourian, 2008). Today, the quality of life is discussed as a key element in policy making and the study of public area policies and referred to as development index. After an initial introduction in the early 1930s, this construct has undergone many changes, and it is increasingly used to measure the progress and development of societies. Since the late 1970s, the interest in the concept of quality of life has increased significantly. From this date onwards, the discussions on the quality of life mostly were focused on the three areas of medicine, psychology, and social sciences. In fact, from the 1930s to the present day, the number of study areas of this construct has been enhanced, leading to the creation of broad literature for the development index.

Keywords: *Communications, Quality of life, Radio, Public service announcement, Citizen, Citizen life, Civic life*

1. Introduction

It should be noted that social modeling is highly effective in changing behaviors and replacing them with new behaviors. The volume of programs produced and broadcasted by the Islamic Republic of Iran Broadcasting (IRIB) has grown significantly in recent years, and the managers of this influential media have always done their best to improve the level of health education at all levels of the society. However, no thorough and comprehensive study has been done so far on the effective rate of the health programs and messages in Iran, while serious studies have been performed in other countries on the impact of education through the media.

As seen, media and the means of mass communication have several and various functions and roles in societies, which increase their importance and place. Regardless of the different categorization about the tasks and functions of the mass media mentioned in this section, in a general view, the functions of mass media can be divided into four news-information providing, educational, entertaining-recreational, and culture-making-nurturing functions.

McQuail (2003) has described different levels of influence of the mass media:

Mass media can affect different levels such as the individual, group or organization, social organization, and the whole community. He has categorized the effects of the means of mass communication as follows:

- Cognitive effects associated with knowledge and belief

- Emotional impacts associated with tendencies and emotions
- Behavioral effects

As a result, he believes that the means of mass communication can

- Produce intended impacts
- Cause unwanted changes
- Create little impact
- Facilitate the change
- Strengthen the existing patterns and values
- Prevent the change

2.Means of mass communication (mass media)

Dansi divides the media into three categories:

- Natural media: They are the media through which ideas are transmitted biologically (through voice, facial expressions, hand gestures, etc.).
- Built (made) media: They are the media through which ideas are represented and transmitted by some made means (books, paintings, statues, letters, etc.).
- Mechanical media: They are the media through which ideas are transmitted by mechanical inventions such as the telephone, the radio, television, the computer, etc. (Densi, 2008: 26).

Undoubtedly, there is a lot of commonality between the built-in and mechanical media. The first one also includes the second one since the mechanical media are actually specific kinds of made media. The "non-biological" media can be divided into three broad categories: Print, electronic and digital. These media essentially differ in terms of what is called the way of expression. Thus, in terms of encoding their messages approach, the print media allow the people to express their verbal messages on the rocks, walls, papyrus, paper and other surfaces or writing system preservatives. Electronic media allow people to express and broadcast their messages through the electronic channel using equipment such as recorder, radio, and television. A recorder is a device that records audio like tape and CD. Radio is an audio system, which provides the ability to send and receive radio signals (electromagnetic waves) in devices called radio. Television (TV) is a system that makes it possible to transmit visual images (pictures) along with sound (voice) in the form of electromagnetic waves, which are converted to their initial forms through receiver devices called the television set. Digital media depend on computer systems such as the Internet (a matrix of networks that connect the computers around the world to each other) and the World Wide Web (a service provider in the Internet that consists of interconnected sites and files and is accessible through a program called the Browser) (Densie, 2008: 26).

All media have a messaging feature. The medium in any type of definition is either the message itself (Marshal McLuhan) or is developed at all for messaging. The message is either the culture itself or is released to transmit or transfer the culture. All mass media have the potential of globalization due to the feature of having massive audiences and the possibility of expanding the communication network (technological feature). The various mass media reflect different events and do this reflection in a variety of ways; some are fast and some are slow. Some are superficial and some others are deep. The distribution zone of some is limited and some of the others are wide (Vahedi, 1997: 54).

2.1.Message

A message is usually a combination of brief and useful words that provide a single image or overall impression of a subject. Message or news is the content of the communication, i.e., a subject that is sent by the sender. The messages can include a wide range of organizational issues that the news source has felt to send them. What matters about a message is its encryption. The message should be put in the form of words such as words, numbers, images, etc., and then sent. Obviously, decryption should be done to understand the meaning and concept of the message. Thus, the true meaning of the news can be realized with the knowledge of the signs used. One "language" must be used in the encryption and decryption (coding and

decoding) of the message by the sender and the receiver. This implies that the sender and receiver must have identical inference and understanding of the symbols and meanings of the words used so that the receiver can realize the sender intention identically (Wiles, 2013).

Communication also represents social interaction (mutual action) through the message. The messages that can be official passwords, symbols or exemplary events of common aspects of a culture. Communication as the name of a process is both specific and general and is both limited and broad in terms of range and scope. Human communication is a collection of precise and clever processes. This communication (no matter how much the message is, or the information giving and taking is simple) is accumulated with hundreds of components (signs, ciphers, and meanings) (Ahmadi, 2001).

Human communication is a diverse set of processes and can use any of dozens of different methods, either words, gestures, states or cards, or intimate conversations, or mass media and the global audiences. Whenever people somehow interact, they actually communicate with each other, and whenever people control each other, they do such a control mainly through communication.

Although communication is an ultimately inclusive concept, it must be emphasized that there is no complete agreement between the researchers about the scope of this term. Some people believe that there will be no communication until the message affects its receiver (Ahmadi, 2001).

Also, the way of providing a message includes the decisions that the source of communication takes to select, adjust arrange the codes and the content. In fact, the method of communication is a set of opportunities for choosing and deciding for the sum of choices about adjusting and arranging the codes and content, and the factors involved in these choices include personality, attitude, knowledge, culture, communication skills and the place in the community both for the message sender and its recipient. In summary, one can say that the combination of code, content, and the method of presenting can produce a wide range of various messages, including materials and the communications style (Wiles, 2013).

A message should be generated after the pre-test and made be available to the target group. Usually, the designers and generators of print media, audiovisual materials, and mass media must perform the pre-test. Unfortunately, most organizations have not the necessary skills or resources to produce printed materials, videotapes or radio programs. Typically, producing local media does not need sophisticated equipment, but it often requires accurate design to ensure that the message has been made available to the target group correctly and at the right time (Wiles, 2013).

.2 Radio

The first wireless system (via electromagnetic waves) to send electrical signals through the air was first called "wireless" and, later, "radiotelegraph" (which is abbreviated as "radio"). The basic scientific principles for radio development were explained by the British physicist, James Clark Maxwell. However, Guglielmo Marconi, an Italian American electrical engineer, used these principles for the invention of the world's first real wireless radio system in 1895. His radio system could send and receive a signal to a distance of up to 3 kilometers.

In 1901, Marcini built an intermittent current generation device that could send signals to a far further distance with less noise. About two decades later, this generator was turned into a commercial technology, which introduced the Radio to the world as the first electronic mass media. In the United States, the first regular publicly scheduled radio broadcast was made from the KDKA Station in Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, in 1920. Subsequently, other stations were established across the United States shortly thereafter, and companies such as the Radio Corporation of America (RCA) and Westinghouse launched radio networks to produce and participate in the production of the programs. In the mid-1920s, radio along with the movies became a popular mass media. In radio, the flows in the field of music, play, advertisement (propaganda) and verbal communication, in general, were made. Compared to print, radio covered more people not only because it immediately covered more distances, but as its audiences did not necessarily have to have printed literacy. Therefore, its planning was done based on the will and demands of the masses. Consequently, the radio created the pop culture- a culture that was for all, not just the "literati" and "scholars." Therefore, radio

created an electronic galaxy, in which an increasingly standard form of distraction emerged for almost anyone to use since radio receivers became cheaper, and thus, the masses could afford to buy them.

The advancement of radio has made a significant impact on increasing the information and knowledge of the people, especially the villagers throughout the world. Rapid, timely and accurate information appears to be an essential element for fighting rumors or reducing the possibility of violence occurring. Due to its low size, having a lot of persuasive and influential forces, advantageous and surprising force, a wide range of distribution and easy usability, radio can play a valuable role in the development process, although it has some disadvantages (Maharati, 2011).

In general, three different periods can be highlighted for radio:

In the first period, the radio was available to the few people who could afford to buy the receiver device as well as certain places like cafes and coffee houses. Also, people usually listened to the radio in groups and collectively. In this period, the radio was dominated mostly by political propaganda.

In the second period, the number of radio devices increased due to the invention of the transistor. Its size became very small so that it could be carried in different places and its price became very inexpensive. During this period, the use of radio became pervasive and private, and the commercial advertising found its way to the radio.

In the third period, radio digitalization (a countless increase of radio broadcast transmitters) and its convergence and compatibility with other media such as Internet radios occurred (listening to radio via mobile phone, PC, and digital TV). In general, the possibility of choosing radio programs has increased in this period by its interactivity, and multiple features of its broadcasting voice have provided opportunities for the listeners and advertisers. The radios of the third era are multidimensional media (Khojasteh, 2002).

The increased role of modern means of mass communication in different parts of human life has led to the use of the high potential of the media in various developments and changes. Accordingly, the role of the media has been highlighted in raising awareness, smoothing and spreading the crises. In other words, as being effective in the weakening of the security bases, the media can also greatly contribute to creating and consolidating them. It should not also be forgotten that the efforts made to use the communication technology in the process of development first began by using the radio. This cheap and flexible medium is still used more than other media in the development projects and almost three-fourths of the developing countries residents use radios (Mohsinian Rad, 1999).

.3 The audience of radio

To determine the number of medium audiences, we must first define the audience. However, there is also ambiguity in the concept of audience terms of application. Before any research on the audience, it must be specified "Who is the target audience?"

There is an ambiguity in terms of use that whether those who have heard all the parts of the program are considered as the listener of the program or those who have accidentally and sporadically heard parts of the program are also seen as the listeners of the program. One of the reasons for the differences between the results of various surveys comes from the different definitions of the audience since the type of audience definition affects the number of audiences. Audience differences regarding the rate of attention to the media content also cause ambiguity in the definition of the audience. This issue has more ambiguity in the case with radio, which is mostly used nowadays as a secondary media (the secondary media concept refers to the issue that the radio listeners often do other activities while listening to the radio, like doing house works and driving, which makes the listener not to have a complete focus on the content of the media). Radio listeners occur in a range of those audiences who use the radio as a non-disturbing background sound (Hearers) to a group looking for a means to focus (Listeners). Sometimes, the listeners are drowned and fascinated by what they hear; on the contrary, they are sometimes so inattentive to the content of the program that make not attempt to understand or recall the contents. Hence, one cannot confidently talk about the higher

effectiveness of radio messages on audiences spending more time listening to the radio (Salemi, 2007: 23, quoted from Chrysler, 2002, 21, 333, 367).

Research provides the main field of radio activities for the development of competitive plans and production of attractive programs tailored to the needs and desires of the audiences and the persuasion of their changing demands. In general, studies can be used in planning for three purposes:

- Identifying the needs of the audiences (needs assessment)
- Finding out their opinions (polls)
- Understanding the effects of a particular program (effect measurement)

Need assessment is usually done before producing a program to get acquainted with the wishes and desires of the audiences and evaluate the amount of their need to produce such a program. In this process, the audiences can be asked to share their opinions about the topic of interest, its presentation format, duration and the play time of the program, the inviting experts, etc., to consider them in the production so that the program would be close to the audiences' wishes. The poll can take place during the broadcast or after the completion of the broadcast of a program to provide the feedback from listeners to planners and administrators. They can use this feedback to fix the shortcomings and modify and correct their program. In case that the broadcast of the program has ended, the views of the audience can be used in future similar programs. The effectiveness assessment is usually used after the completion of the broadcast of a program or a set of programs to measure the impact rate of a program on the audience, the type and the quality of such effectiveness, which results can be greatly used in future planning (Azar Dashti, 2010, p. 54).

Measuring the number of the audiences of each station is done using the following four methods:

- An average number of the audiences: Based on this method, the number of the audience of a station is estimated through measuring the number of the audiences of the programs of that station for a certain period of time, for example, 15 minutes.
- Cumulative calculation method: In this method, the sum of those who have listened to the programs of a radio station in a particular time situation, for example, 5 minutes or a day or a week, is calculated.
- Main core method: In this method, the number of listeners that the station is actually their first choice is calculated. In other words, these audiences are those who prefer this station to other stations.
- Participatory: In this method, a percentage of all listeners are considered that listen to the programs of a station in the targeted consumer market (Handi, 2008: 165).

Two goals can be considered to examine the factors influencing the increase or decrease of the effects due to the relationship between the audience and the radio:

- A .Examining the relationship between the exposure to the radio programs and acceptance of cultural changes
- B .Classification of the audiences based on the modernization rate with respect to the hours of using the radio and the quality of use

1.3.1 Categorization of radio networks (stations) in terms of the program making

In terms of producing programs and broadcasting, the radio stations can be divided into three types:

- A. Public radios
- B. Private radios
- C. Specialized radios

A . Public radios

They refer to radio stations that produce programs in all main topics and for all levels of the audiences by different and several program making methods. The subjects of radio program production are generally as follows: Religious, cultural, social, economic, historical, political, news, literary, artistic, sports, entertainment, general information, military and scientific. However, some other topics are also considered in some other radio stations, which can be categorized as part of these topics.

B .Private radios

Private radios are radio stations established for specific audiences or specific audience groups. However, they produce programs in all or most of the topics and subjects in terms of theme and content. They produce their programs with a specific style, and program making approaches tailored to the age group of the audience or the psychological and social requirements of the specific audiences of the station according to the time requirements, environmental changes and the special tastes of their audiences. Radio Javan (The Youth) station is a typical example of this kind of radio station in Iran.

C .Specialized radios

Specialized radios are those formed based on a particular subject area, which does not produce programs out of their own specific domain. Naturally, these stations have a specific type of audience. They cover their own target audiences in terms of occupation or profession, age range, education, interests, and special topics and subjects such as music, art or other subjects. Radio Salamat (Health) is an example of specialized radio stations in Iran. In classifying radios, many radio stations can be regarded as both private and specialized radios. Radio Maaref is an example of such kind of radios in Iran.

There are common grounds in comprehensive planning for a radio, whether public, private or specialized. Specialized radios, while adhering to a systematic structure and common features in producing programs, have a special structure in management and planning as well.

.4 Radio: A public service

Some people think market forces provide the best possible radio and TV services to people. However, we believe in the World Radio-Television Council that radio and television is an arena related to the interests of the community and, like education, public policies and public institutions should serve the citizens, Radio has such a duty as well. We believe that there is no need to sacrifice independence and freedom of speech to achieve such a goal (Saghebfar, 2011: 19).

The main reason for the establishment of public radio institutions was the robust belief in the fundamental mismatch between the public service function and other functions, in particular, gaining the highest profit (Saghebfar, 2011: 32). Almost all of the world's democratic systems have considered a place for public services in their radio and television mechanisms. This decision is partly due to the idea that Radio, and then TV, are special media. As radio and television use limited resources in terms of the frequency spectrum and they are supposed to benefit from a great social, political and cultural power and their producers have privileges; they have been considered "ethics-based" media, which is well summarized in the term "public service." This also results partly from the awareness of the market incompetence and failure. Thus, it is believed that a fully commercialized system cannot respond to all expectations (Blamer, 1991).

In fact, all governments actually interfere in the rules on allocation of frequencies - whether to private or public radio stations. An important thing is the technical nature of radio broadcasting, which has made the government intervention necessary. The Hertz limited frequencies are considered a part of the territory as a rare source, which should be exploited in the public interest. Each citizen, having a radio receiver, could instantly access information cultural products that such access would not be possible in any other way in the absence of radio (Saghebfar, 2011).

Countries should insist more on a positive aspect, i.e., the achievements that the radio can provide in the area of public services. I am not against trading. We need more trading and more economic activity, but we also need better and more education and training, more enlightenment and more understanding of what's going

on around the world. We also need all of these for all people, since, in a democratic system, it is the individual who has the right and, fortunately, sometimes the possibility to participate in the basic political choices. Today, in the vast arena of culture, one can hardly find a task more important than rethinking about the role of radio in education, citizenship rights, democratic values and intellectual enrichment of the communities and the individuals forming those societies. What both the imagination power and the statesmen need is an area in which the profit would not be the main motive; that is, for all people, whether in developed or developing countries, some materials will be provided for thinking and imagining so that everyone can be a truly liberal and free citizen and a creative human being (Saghebfar, 2011: 22).

In the last three decades, the attention of policymakers and planners of the world's governments, including the Islamic Republic of Iran, has tended toward the production and distribution of a variety of promotional and advertising messages called public service announcements. The purpose of their dissemination includes the achievement of national and regional development, providing better conditions and qualities for people's lives, maintaining national resources and reserves, correcting the improper practices and models of life, and personal and social behaviors, etc. (Jabbarlo Shabestari and Hadavinia, 2011).

At the beginning of the emergence of radio, many discussions took place about its organization to maximize the use of its potential features. Almost everywhere in the world, radio has been considered as a social and cultural development tool rather than an economic activity. Radio was initially considered to be basically a cultural device. Radio organizations such as theaters, museums, operas, symphony orchestras, universities and the educational system were known as a part of the community, which mission was to enrich and promote the linguistic, literary, spiritual, aesthetic and ethnic heritage of the community (Rowland and Tracey, 1990).

In the field of politics, radio was considered to be a means of informing citizens about state affairs. Also, many countries came to the conclusion that they need to ensure that the ruling party or political class does not dominate this media for its own benefit for providing better information to the citizens. Thus, in these democratic systems, it seemed to be necessary to guarantee the political independence of the radio (Saghebfar, 2011).

In the social context, it was believed that radio could play special roles, and undoubtedly, the most important of these was its educational role: Education by attracting people's attention to some social problems and issues, education through broad dissemination and broadcasting of various scientific programs (Saghebfar, 2011).

At the cultural level, radio undoubtedly could create new interests among people for different cultural products. It was thought that music, shows (plays), books, etc. should be introduced to people with this communication device. In the same way, radio was also an effective means for creators of works to identify themselves and contact with the public (Saghebfar, 2011).

McQuail (1998) reminds that although there are numerous examples of financing in the past through commercial sources, especially commercial advertisements, however, there is no European country whose revenue has been balanced through commercials. According to very common policy, radio had not to be dominated by profitability, but the priority was given to the allowed broadcasters complying with the exact terms and conditions so that they were not able to bring the programs merely to the area of profitability. Hence, that policy provided them with a "space" that could be used for cultural or social purposes, which were not necessarily money-makers.

➤ . Dimensions of urban quality of life

Most researchers and scholars define two objective and subjective dimensions for the concept of urban quality of life. Each dimension has more detailed components and dimensions. Dysart and Deller believe that "the quality of a person's life depends on the exterior and objective facts of his life and inner and subjective perception of these external facts and objective conditions as well as himself. The concept of urban quality of life in urban planning can be used at least in two stages of the planning process. The first

stage is when the planners intend to have an accurate and reliable picture of the city's current situation. At this phase, the planners seek to focus on priorities and issues that matter more. In this context, evaluating the various dimensions of urban quality of life can serve as a very good guide and model for them (Lotfi, 2009: 69).

The second stage is when the programs and projects have to be evaluated to determine their usefulness, effectiveness and success rate. At this stage, examining the effects of these programs and projects on different dimensions of urban quality of life can similarly provide a good guide for the planners and decision-makers (Lotfi, 2009: 68 and 69). With a review of the definitions of quality of life, the conceptual context of quality of life can be considered to have the following dimensions: Objective facts, subjective perception, enjoyment, well-being, satisfaction with life, providing human needs, health, welfare, and so on. The urban quality of life is usually measured through subjective indicators derived from surveying and evaluating the citizens' perceptions and satisfaction with urban life or via using objective indicators derived from secondary data, and rarely by using both types of indicators (Rezvani et al., 2009: 87). However, some recent studies have tried to provide a hybrid index for the study of urban quality of life by combining objective and subjective indicators. The argument was based on the lack of correlation between the results of the objective dimension and the results of the subjective measurement of the quality of life. In research entitled "What are the strengths of the relationship between objective and subjective indices of urban quality of life?", McCraea et al. (2006) developed a new and innovative approach to measuring the urban quality of life in the relevant literature (McCraea, 2006: 84).

Therefore, all definitions of quality of life can be categorized into three categories of objectivistic definitions, subjectivistic definitions, and combined definitions. The objectivist definitions are mostly based on macro-social data and statistical reports, which are obtained through official surveys or reports, including the structural, social, economic, material, and physical objective conditions and situations of a region or an environment. Examples in this context may involve children mortality rates, life expectancy at birth, gross domestic product, per capita income, ratio of dentist to total population, ratio of hospital bed to total population, per capita of park and green space, per capita of field sports, per capita area of housing and the like. The subjective-oriented definitions are based on feelings, beliefs, tendencies, the feeling of need, sense of deprivation and the interests of the inhabitants of an area, which involve the sense of satisfaction and feeling of happiness of living in an area. The combined definitions rely on the combination of these two and seek to achieve a more reliable indicator of the quality of life by measuring both objective and subjective dimensions.

Schneider (1976) used the six dimensions of income and employment, environment, health, education, participation and social harms to assess the quality of life in American cities (Massam, 2003: 123). In another study examining the urban quality of life in Toronto, five dimensions of economic life, environment, the health of the community, transportation and security were considered to measure the urban quality of life (Toronto Urban Health, 1993: 198).

➤ literature review

In their article, Faraji et al. (2010) studied the dimensions of urban quality of life in the urban regions and areas of Iran based on official statistics. In this study, the Morris model was used to measure the quality of life, in which the purchasing power, the level of literacy, and the life expectancy were measured as components of the quality of life. Of the 253 cities surveyed, only 24 cities (9.5%) were identified as good quality. Nearly 50% of the urban areas studied were known to be of the deprived areas. Tehran as an inhomogeneous urban region has separated itself from other urban areas. The uneven distribution of national investment in different sectors has led to a development gap of up to 3.9. According to the above researchers, the relevant index of the value of 1 indicates the severity of the development failure.

Ghalibaf and Rostaei (2011) used a combined index in their article to study the urban quality of urban life in the Yaftabad neighborhood of Tehran, which had four dimensions of transportation quality, the quality of the economic environment, the quality of the social environment and the quality of physical environment.

The situation of three economic, social and environmental dimensions was assessed as undesirable, and only the transport situation was evaluated to be at an optimal level.

In their article, Maleki and Habibi (2011) studied the quality of the environment and the sustainability of urban neighborhoods by an objective approach. While establishing a link between sustainability and the quality of the environment, they measured the quality of the environment in four general environmental, social and cultural, economic and physical categories.

Ghaffari Nasab (2012) analytically and descriptively explained the role of active citizenship in the quality of life in his article and emphasized the strengthening of active citizenship role.

In their article, Vesali and Tavakol (2012) examined the impact of social capital on the urban quality of life in Tehran. A high correlation was found in this study between social capital, especially on the trust dimension, and the urban quality of life.

In their article, Zanjani and Qarahi (2011) evaluated the role of educational TV commercials of Islamic Republic of Iran Television in developing and expanding citizenship education (Case study of Districts 2 and 18 of the city of Tehran). Their findings showed that the factors of education level, residential area, audiences' jobs, advertising time, and satisfaction with the broadcast of advertisements were effective in paying attention to the educational advertisements. In addition, the time of ads broadcast has affected the audience's satisfaction. Paying attention to the educational ads has made the audiences to comply with the educational content of advertisements and attention to the behavior of citizens, which has led to the development of citizenship education. With the better presentation of these advertisements, responsible and committed citizens can be trained associated with increased hope for their contribution to the development and advancement of the community.

Dadgari and Jafari (2010) analyzed the content of Radio Javan commercial advertising with an emphasis on cultural and social values in their article. The results indicated that despite the emphasis of the ideological institutions of society on ethical and religious values, the commercial advertisements broadcasted from radio promote and expand the values based on making wealth and increasing welfare and the value of the religion has the lowest share of the promoting values. In a general look at the status of radio advertising, it should be noted that unfortunately, in Iran, all radio capabilities are not used to supply commercial advertisements. The commercial advertising capacity of radio is barely used. Radio is seen as space and media for the owners of ads to re-submit their TV commercials and remind their images in the minds of their audience. The commercial advertising on the radio is in the focus of attention of the advertisers due to its lower costs. However, in return for this high-end product, there is no attempt to improve the quality of advertising, and the sensitivities in television advertising are not adhered to in the radio. Perhaps, neglecting in paying attention to the delicacies of the production has led to forgetting the effectiveness of the messages reflecting from the advertisement. As a result, promoting the cultural-social values of wealth and prosperity has become the priority of these ads, or perhaps, the lack of radio media funds has made it play a variety of commercials despite its rich background in the culture-making of this country.

In his dissertation, Nematollahi (2001) examined the role of mass communication media in the training of optimum consumption of electricity from the perspective of the experts in the electric power industry. The results indicated that the highest number of the statistical population studied has paid attention to the impact of mass media in the regulating of electricity consumption behavior and educational advertising. A majority of people surveyed pointed out to the effect of mass media on children. On the other hand, a large number of the studied people believed that the broadcasting time of these messages is inadequate. The highest role of mass media is in regulating the power consumption behavior, and the use of messages is focused on saving and optimizing the power consumption. The role of mass media in regulating power consumption behavior and conducting educational and cultural activities aimed at saving regardless of the economic and cultural class and the level of education can play a role in increasing the motivation for saving.

Fedaei Mehraban (2007) explored the urbanization, media and social well-being (the role of the media of societies in transition in the social health of citizens) in his article. He stated that the urban health is about

social health more than anything since urbanization is a social phenomenon. On the one hand, the existential philosophy of the mass media can be defined in the form of collective living and social life. Therefore, one can say that social health, media, and urban life are inherently interconnected, and hence, attention to media is highly important in the engineering of social health and urban life. The present paper reveals that how the modernism neglect about the urban life in the West has caused many problems in the area of social health. Obviously, the media can also be a two-edged sword in this regard. That is, they can move towards the destruction of social health and also participate in its re-production as the public media are the most important modeling institution in each society.

Jabbarlo Shabestari and Hadavinia (2011) addressed the reasons for the need for public education programs of traffic culture in the children and adolescent audience area by focusing on public services TV advertisements in their article. According to them, to address all segments of the society, especially children and adolescents, the institutions and organizations responsible for transportation and transport safety of the country need to more focus on necessary measures related to the production and distribution of such advertising-educational messages (public service television commercials) to provide more grounds for dissemination of patterns related to safe and non-risky behaviors, or more precisely, observance of driving guidelines to make them continuous and institutionalized behaviors more than ever. Also, due to the flooding and synergic effects of public service TV commercials on traffic culture within the community, the staff of the deputy of the NAJA and the IRIB authorities need to put in their agenda to produce television programs for children and adolescents in the form of cartoon series with the presence of popular characters to promote such educational messages.

In his dissertation titled as "Pathology of commercial advertisements and presenting an optimal model (Case study: Radio Payam in the fourth quarter of 2008), Hasi (2012) stated that the people knowledge of goods and services seems essential to an individual and social need in this era of communications that the media have become powerful and engaging in everything. The media play an important role in this regard by providing informing. In the meantime, the radio continues to perform well, and a vast majority of people in the community still continue to receive the information they need from this media. As on the radio, the message is received and perceived based on individual experience, the Radio can provide the audience with the necessary and sufficient information about the product or service in question and encourage them to choose and buy the intended goods or services by inducing the psychological effect and through establishing an intimate and friendly relationship with them. Therefore, one can say that the radio as an independent media has the necessary conditions for the production and distribution of its special advertisements. The recognition and knowledge of producing radio advertising based on the subject and structure refer to the necessity and importance of this research.

In his article, Dehghani (2014) studied the role of media in the mental health of the community by examining the pathology, finding the roots of the challenges and the restorative role of media in the family and the society. The results of this study to create and improve the family and community's health by the media were as follows:

- Friendly training , control, and monitoring by parents
- Teaching the use and cultural utilization of the media to parents and presenting a curriculum with this name in schools and universities
- Networking and scheduling the broadcast of media audiovisual programs
- Assessment the audience spectrum and producing programs based on the age of the audience
- Most importantly, self-care education against the misuse of high-risk media for the general population

5 .Research findings

This was an applied study in terms objective and descriptive-surveying research in terms of methodology, which was conducted using a questionnaire. The statistical population was categorized into two parts of stations directors and administrators and citizens. The first section included all managers (planners and program makers) and producers of the networks of the deputy of IRIB (350 subjects). The citizen's section included all citizens of Tehran. The sampling was done in the first section with simple random sampling

method, while the multi-stage cluster sampling method was used in the second part. The sample size of the study in both sections was obtained at 67 and 331, respectively, using the Morgan table. The research measurement tool was a researcher-made questionnaire entitled as "The Role of Short Cultural Radio Messages (Public Service Announcement) in Enhancing the Quality of Civic Life." The face and content validities of the questionnaire were confirmed by the relevant professors and experts. Its reliability was also confirmed by performing a pilot project on 30 sample individuals through the Cronbach's alpha test. Then, the questionnaires were distributed among the samples.

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data gathered from both sections. The components of frequency, frequency percentage, mean and standard deviation were used in the descriptive statistics section. In the inferential statistics section, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to examine the data distribution. The Exploratory Factor Analysis was employed to identify the components of the civic quality of life affected by the radio public service announcements. Also, the single -sample t-test was used to investigate the role of radio public service announcements in enhancing the civic quality of life. Finally, the Friedman's rating test was applied to prioritize the components of the civic quality of life influenced by radio public service announcements. All statistical operations were performed using the SPSS software Ver. 22.

The research results indicated that 10 indicators of quality of life can be considered in radio programs, including "economic knowledge and saving", "attention to the environment and traffic culture", "increased spirituality", "promotion of physical literacy", "art-orientation", "social health and altruism", "optimal use of leisure times", "attention to physical and mental health", "life expectancy and happiness" and "information provision". Also, radio public service announcements appeared to have a significant role in enhancing all indicators of the civic quality of life ($P < 0.05$). Finally, a significant difference was found between the indicators of civic quality of life influenced by public service announcements from the perspective of the research samples ($\text{Sig} = 0.001$, $X^2 = 46.187$). Thus, "attention to mental and physical health" and "life expectancy and happiness" had the highest priorities and "increasing spirituality" and "optimal use of leisure times" showed the lowest priorities.

Quality of life is a multi-dimensional concept and encompasses various objective and subjective, material and spiritual, quantitative and qualitative, individual and social, micro and macro aspects and the like. In the objective and material dimensions, the quality of life includes living standards, infrastructure facilities, economic production, employment, prices, law, health, entertainment, leisure times, culture and art, and so on. In the subjective, qualitative and spiritual dimensions, the quality of life involves personal experiences and perceptions, the feeling of security, and the sense of satisfaction of people from living in the city. Since the quality of a person's life depends on the external and objective facts of life and his inner and subjective perception of these external truths and objective conditions as well as himself, thus, this variable seems to be affected by many factors. The quality of life depends on exogenous forces such as production technology, infrastructures, relations with other groups or the country, community institutions, natural environment as well as the endogenous factors, including interactions in the society and the values of an individual or a community. However, to engage in community and interacting with others, the individuals need social skills, including the ability to exchange thoughts in social relationships, awareness of the role and social values, understanding various social situations (normal and critical), problem-solving ability, playing an effective social role, etc. Social skills are transmitted to people in three main ways: Family, media and school. Meanwhile, media influence, even in the family and school areas, is as such that one could hardly imagine to enjoy modern living facilities without them. In fact, the mass media are one of the factors capable of affecting the culture and urban life. In today's modern world, the role of the media has increased so much that the life cannot be imagined without their presence. Radio is one of these mass media in which the radio program makers are trying to communicate with their audience in a variety of methods to transmit their messages to them. One of the ways of influencing the audience is the use of short-term program making templates in an attractive and engaging approach. The Public Service Announcements are messages, announcements, or reports, which broadcast is aimed to publicize the government programs, educational projects, voluntary services or social reform. They are broadcasted free of charge from radio and television stations and are in the public interest. The public service announcements are produced aimed at raising

awareness, changing attitudes and public behavior by focusing on a social problem or issue with a duration usually less than two minutes. The frequent playing of these messages, in fact, highlights one or more topics at a specific time period and tries to change the general behavior of the audience through influencing the cognitive domain and the use of emotional stimuli. With regard to these issues, it seems that radio cultural announcements (public service announcements) are related to the attitudes of people and their quality of life. Therefore, this research was carried out and its findings were discussed below.

According to the results of exploratory factor analysis, 38 items of the research questionnaire could be reduced to 10 factors. By combining these 38 items, we were able to design a new structure based on factors with a new combination and analyze the data accordingly. The factors discovered were named as follows: "Economic knowledge and saving", "Attention to the environment and traffic culture", "Increasing spirituality", "Promotion of physical literacy", "Art-orientation", "Social health and altruism", "Optimal use of leisure times", "Attention to physical and mental health", "Life expectancy and happiness" and "Information provision". According to this result, the ten factors mentioned can be considered in improving the civic quality of life indicators using the short radio messages in PSA(public service announcement) format. One of these factors is "economic knowledge and saving." Consumption is one of the three important factors in the field of economics, and its knowledge since consumption and its quality forms one of the three main components of the economy and neglecting it also affects the other two parts. The interactions of the economic triples, namely, production, distribution, and consumption, are not overlooked. Therefore, in the divine teachings, a part of the economic issues is devoted to the issue of consumption. The teachings of the Qur'an organize all being in the justice system so that they have examined and carefully criticized the exclusion of justice in any subject, including economic matter and in each of the economic triples. Thus, the inappropriate and excessive consumption has been equaled to oppression with punishment in both material and spiritual worlds. Considering the inappropriate and excessive consumption as an oppression crime and sin is due to the fact that any injustice leads to the departure of the goals and the philosophy of creation. Hence, any action at any level that is contrary to justice and the purposes of creation would be introduced as a departure from creation, justice and divine philosophy, which requires proper punishments. Accordingly, one can say that contentment and saving are not only good but also a valued behavior and must be considered and emphasized ethically and religiously. With these interpretations, it is clear that radio public service announcements can be a suitable tool for promoting and improving the economic knowledge of families, on the one hand, and developing the culture of contentment and saving by relying on the Qur'an and multiple hadiths on the other hand. Radio public service announcements contain messages that give citizens information about job opportunities, teaches the citizens the ways to increase income and wealth by programs, and by providing some messages, help the citizens improve their economic situation, and in general, they will raise the citizen's economic awareness.

Another indicator of the civic quality of life affected by radio public service announcements is the "attention to the environment and traffic culture." As the living context for humans to live, the city plays a major role in creating a sense of satisfaction, and it actually shapes the lifestyle of man and determines the quality of his life. Therefore, attention to the physical environment of the city by researchers of various sciences plays an important role in improving the quality of human life. Just like that the home should have certain attributes and benefits to make a living and settlement comfortable and peaceful, the city also needs to have qualities and features to provide comfort, relief, and security. Today, the physical development of cities, the growth of industry, urbanization and population growth in cities, distance from nature and disconnection of the human beings from the natural environment lead to excessive and unsustainable urban development, degradation of urban green areas and rising demand for urban land, which in turn cause the disappearance of green spaces within the city, reduced share of urban gardens and land use change. Such things are occurring while urban green spaces, as an essential and integral part of the unique body of cities, play a fundamental role in their metabolism, which shortage can cause serious disturbances in the life of cities. Therefore, the creation and development of green space play a major role in the quality of life of all creatures, including humans. On the other hand, the massive accumulation of population in the small towns has caused obvious problems like pollution and traffic and lowered the quality of life of citizens. Air pollution and traffic have similar effects on life. Air pollution causes an increase in the mortality rate and shortens the lifespan of residents of urban areas. By wasting time, traffic also reduces the useful time for other activities, and thus,

negatively affects the quality of life of citizens. In this regard, by increasing the environmental information of citizens as well as making them interested in environmental issues, radio public service announcements can push them to improve the situation and enhance the quality of life.

"Increasing spirituality" is another factor associated with the quality of life. In the modern times of mankind, in spite of all the advancements and possibilities, dissatisfaction with life is evident as a problem for families and communities. Every day, the number of people who believe that spirituality is a factor affecting the quality of life and a treatment for their suffering and helplessness, and the number of specialists who focus and concentrate on spiritual beliefs and behaviors to treat illnesses and maintain the health are increasing. Today's man has come with consciousness and insight to the idea that he will be alone without spirituality and will be drown in the technology whirlwind. Thus, he has come to the conclusion that one of the best ways to save himself is spirituality and strengthening the spiritual beliefs. Accordingly, in recent years, researchers have paid more attention to spirituality and spiritual well-being to improve the quality of life. They suggest that there is an extraordinary force in believing in God that gives man a kind of spiritual power and helps him enduring the hardships of everyday life and saves him from the anxiety and concerns that many people are exposed to. Thus, spirituality can improve the quality of human life. In this regard, the role of mass media, including radio, is unique since the radio programs contain useful religious and Islamic information, which try to improve the lives of the citizens by providing religious and spiritual programs. In addition, radio can "promote physical literacy", which is another aspect of the quality of life. It is not a secret that physical health and lack of disease can improve the quality of life. However, numerous medical research indicates the positive effects of exercise and physical activity on the physical and mental health of people. People with inadequate physical mobility, in addition to high treatment costs, suffer from mental illnesses and do not enjoy the life much. Therefore, they need to increase their physical literacy (and, more specifically, their mobility literacy) to enjoy a healthy life. Mobility literacy includes mastering basic motor skills and basic sports skills, which empowers people to interpret their environment and make the right decisions for a safe and controlled movement in a wide range of physical activity conditions. It supports long-term participation and the best performance of the individual due to his abilities. Hence, with the appropriate physical literacy, people can have an active life and enjoy the benefits of mental and physical health. In this regard, radio public service announcements in relation to types of sports, useful physical activities for different ages, proper and correct nutrition, etc. can improve the physical literacy and, consequently, enhance the quality of life.

Another factor of the urban quality of life can be referred to as "love of art." Everyday activities and conflicts of life have swallowed the members of the community. It seems that all the life has been summed up in vividness and economic and social progress. People do not have time anymore for their glamorous preoccupations, including arts. This is while all human beings have a personality in themselves that is heavily interested in art. The man likes to be an audience of works of art and enjoy them. That is why seeing the pristine nature or the sunset vivifies a childish cheer within him. For the same reason, when a good poem is played along with music and a high-quality tuning, he raises the sound of the speakers and wants to listen to it 100 times more. Art is a human and international language. Undoubtedly, art is the manifestation of beauties whose original creator is God, and these are the artists who portray them. Anyway, by expressing a tendency toward a variety of arts, whether in the form of an artist or as an audience of art, man enjoys this phenomenon, which affects the quality of his life. Radio programs enhance the citizens' awareness and information about art and with the broadcast of various cultural and artistic programs such as music and the introduction of cultural-artistic venues like cinemas, theaters, museums, galleries, etc. encourage them to visit these places. Therefore, the radio can lead the people toward art with such programs.

"Social health and altruism" is also another factor that must be considered in the urban quality of life. One of the characteristics of people with social health is altruism. Altruism can be defined as follows: It is a behavior intending to help others even when nothing is gained or no benefits are expected. The question now is why people behave as such. One of the main attitudes in this regard is the theory of social exchange, which believes that both the helper and the one is helped do practically exchange of benefits. As a result, kindness (altruism) is not really free of expectation. Researchers have reminded that many people have a sense of sympathy. That is, they are distracted and disturbed when they see someone disturbing and when

the suffering of others ends, they feel relief. Therefore, while some helps might be done due to enjoying from a reward like a pleasant feeling, some other assistance are intended solely to assist those who need the help. The experiments to test this view have come to the conclusion that sympathy often leads to helping behaviors as the helper believes that someone else will really get that help and he does care whether that person will know who has helped him. Other scholars believe that the social norms will form the acts of kindness. Thus, the role of mass media in defining and promoting social norms can be highlighted in this regard since nowadays, the mass media has turned into an instrument in the hands of governments to define and develop social norms, and in general, to promote the community culture and the radio media is following this rule as well. Radio public service announcements have the ability to give citizens a more positive look and reduce the division of the ethnic groups and the various strata of the people, and generally promote the social cohesion. In the same vein, there is another component called "Optimal use of leisure times". Leisure times refer to the time appearing for people after doing their daily tasks, during which, people get busy doing their favorite activities. The way of spend leisure time varies according to the age, gender, economic status, social status, etc. However, how to spend leisure time reflects the cultural characteristics of the community. Spending leisure time in the current age has become so diverse due to the vast development in all cultural, social and economic areas. Everyone in the community, depending on their tendencies and tastes, try to spend their free time in a way to best suits their needs in this context. Leisure times guarantee the human health and mental health. Continuous and uninterrupted intellectual and practical employment causes physical and mental exhaustion in such a way that the individual loses his vitality and exhilaration. It sometimes provides the ground for a variety of mental disorders. With these interpretations, spending leisure time with positive methods and programs appears to be essential and effective on the quality of life. One of the ways to spend leisure time is to use mass media such as radio.

Another indicator of quality of life is "attention to physical and mental health." In general, healthcare is defined as maintaining and promotion health, preventing diseases and increasing the mental, physical and social strength of people who have become weak due to illness. By adhering to hygiene, everyone can keep himself physically, psychologically and socially well and in a proper fit and done his duties well for himself and his family and community. Physical health is related to the absence of diseases. Disease is the opposite of comfort and physical health. Physical health is obtained by caring for his body health through exercises, stimulating the mind, right nutrition, etc. In general, changing the lifestyle, appropriate exercises and practice, healthy nutrition, good social relationships and mental activity helps to avoid diseases and medical problems. On the other hand, the character, whether healthy or unhealthy, depends on the culture. Culture is an obstacle or supporter of the positive development and growth of human beings. Eric Forum considers the human personality mostly a product of culture. In his view, mental health depends on the extent to which society meets the basic needs of the rather than the extent that an individual adapts himself to the society. As a result, mental health is a social issue more than an individual issue. An unhealthy community creates hostility, suspicion and distrust among its members and prevents their full growth and development. In contrast, a healthy society allows its members to love each other, to be fruitful, efficient, and creative, and foster the power of their reasonableness and objectivity. It should be noted that mass media such as radio and television are one of the tools for the change and development of the community culture.

"Life expectancy and happiness" is another component of the urban quality of life. Life expectancy is an issue that has been very much considered due to its importance in the societies. Life expectancy index is a criterion for measuring the average lifespan of a society. This criterion shows us that every person should at least expect how many years to live in a country where he was born. Due to numerous scientific studies conducted in this area, various and several factors affect the life expectancy index. Optimizing and taking such factors serious, the life expectancy in any country can be increased. The most important factors affecting the life expectancy index include the approach to provide health care services, the level of health education in the inclusive media, the common lifestyle, the quantity and quality of individual and social stresses, the amount of permissible and public joys and happiness, environmental health and economic conditions of the country. In this regard, the role of the mass media, and in particular radio, must be taken seriously as the radio can promote the life expectancy and the happiness of the citizens by providing appropriate cultural programs as well as creating the ground for happiness and joy in the society by using funny and comic programs. In addition, radio messages make people feel secure and relaxed, and by

providing social programs affect the satisfaction of the social relationship of the citizens. Also, they teach respect in the family to citizens and through increasing public trust in citizens, they increase hope for the future in them. Finally, the information providing function of the radio should not be neglected. For example, making the people aware and interested in sports, exercise and physical activity can lead to the resolution of health problems, which affects in turn the people's quality of life. The radio can broaden the public's vision horizon on the issues by producing and broadcasting sports, economic, political, and health news and pave the way for the development and improvement of the quality of life of the people in the community through shaping the public opinions and the development of collective thoughts. Meanwhile playing a key role in informing, mass media are one of the most valuable and economic resources to improve the quality of life that provide all the details with a good quality to the public. However, it should be noted that the media, along with the positive and important roles for the quality of life, can have a destructive and negative effect if they are used inappropriately. The most important negative effects of the media on the quality of life can be the expansion of rumors and creating disagreement, conflicts and disorder, weakening of morale and exaggerating the negative issues. If the mass media publish fake and unrealistic news and challenging rumors, they will cause stress and anxiety among people, and thus, reduce their quality of life. Therefore, radio programs producers should be cautious about selecting different programs and news and will improve the quality of life of the citizens by providing useful and desirable information.

Considering the result of the single-sample t-test, radio public service announcements have a significant role in improving all indicators of civic quality of life ($P > 0.05$). Today's society is unthinkable without the means of mass communication. The mass media are important for communities and have diverse functions depending on the kind of system that the media is subordinate to as well as the interests and needs of specific individuals and the development rate of that society. The indirect communication created through the prestigious press, and especially the modern communication media such as radio and television among massive human groups is called "mass or collective communication." It should be noted that the communications established through the radio in the mass societies have also a direct aspect since the speech of the radio broadcaster is heard by the listeners instantaneous and direct. However, it should not be forgotten that, contrary to direct communication in its specific sense, which is face-to-face and mutual, the direct radio communication is a one-way communication, and neither the speakers nor the listeners know each other and cannot show a direct reaction to each other. With all these interpretations, it should be considered that the social norms of every society, from the family to one country and even the entire world, can be strengthened or weakened by using the media as powerful tools for the change and development of people's lifestyles. In fact, using the mass media such as radio and television, various issues related to the quality of life can be promoted and encouraged to improve them in the community. By producing radio programs in the form of different stories or narratives, the importance of altruism and assistance to fellow human beings in human society and its benefits can be promoted and improved in the society. Also, by promoting economic knowledge and saving in citizens, the household expenses can be reduced to improve their livelihoods consequently. Radio messages raise the citizens' economic awareness and help them to improve their economic situation. In the same vein, radio encourages people to use public transport with reports of cultural messages, and as a training medium, can reduce traffic levels in the city. This, in addition to its direct benefits, including preventing the citizens' waste of time in traffic, will provide more attention to the environment. However, environmental messages can also be directly focused on the radio programs.

6 Summary & Conclusion

In the present era, people are more interested in media such as TV and the Internet. But still, the radio has its audience, and some people have their spare time listening to radio programs. Attractive radio programs are effective in filling the leisure time of citizens and educate them to use their leisure time usefully. Also, they inform the citizens about parks and recreation centers and encourage citizens to make a happy and fun life by providing useful and expert information. The basic task of the mass media, including radio, is to equip people with awareness and information they need to live in a changing world. On the other hand, the information required by individuals is different, and information should be provided in all areas of the people's needs. In this regard, the results suggest that "attention to mental and physical health" and "life

expectancy and happiness" have the highest priorities in the development of quality of life. It seems that the programs related to mental and physical health and life expectancy and happiness are produced more than other programs, or they have had a greater impact than others.

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